

Calibrating the Regolith X-ray Imaging Spectrometer (REXIS)

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes the onboard calibration process of REXIS (the Regolith X-ray Imaging Spectrometer), an instrument on OSIRIS-REx. OSIRIS-REx, scheduled to be launched in 2016, is a planetary mission intending to return a regolith sample from a near Earth asteroid called Bennu. REXIS, a student-led collaboration between Harvard and MIT, is a soft X-ray (0.5-7.5 keV) coded-aperture telescope with four X-ray CCDs and a gold coated stainless steel mask. REXIS will measure the surface elemental abundance of Bennu by capturing X-ray fluorescence (XRF) lines induced by solar X-ray flux. For the energy calibration of the XRF lines, REXIS will use a set of onboard ^{55}Fe radioactive sources (which generate 5.89 keV lines) placed alongside the X-ray CCDs. To ensure that the activity level of the ^{55}Fe sources is adequate for in-flight calibration, we have measured and analyzed the CCD response to various ^{55}Fe activity levels for the REXIS engineering model (EM). We also characterized the spectral resolution, the gain, and the uniformity of the EM CCDs through spectral line fitting.

1. Introduction

Asteroid research supports many scientific endeavours. It provides insight on what materials were present during early solar system formation and also what primordial chemicals may have given rise to life on Earth. Asteroid research allows us to calculate the probabilities of asteroid impact with Earth and to hypothesize how the impact would affect us. Finally, searching for and studying mineral rich asteroids provides the foundation for possibly mining asteroids in the future, perhaps generating revenue to fund future space exploration.

Near Earth asteroids are easier to study targets for such inquiries. Though many planetary science missions have studied asteroids, none have done what OSIRIS-REx has proposed to do: return a significant sample of the asteroid back to Earth.

1.1. OSIRIS-REx

OSIRIS-REx, the third New Frontiers mission sponsored by NASA, is scheduled to be launched in 2016. Its scientific objective is twofold. First, it will observe and characterize the properties of a near-Earth asteroid, Bennu (1999 RQ36), which is a scientifically interesting and hazardous object (See 1.2). Instruments on OSIRIS-REx will determine the distribution, chemistry, mineralogy, and non-gravitational orbital motion of Bennu. The composition information will be used to calibrate telescopic data of Bennu and other similar asteroids. The observed non-gravitational motion, primarily from the Yarkovsky effect¹, will allow better prediction of the future orbital path of Bennu, a worthy task due to the proximity of the asteroid to Earth and potential for impact. Secondly, OSIRIS-REx will attempt a feat not yet accomplished; it will capture and return to Earth a significant

¹The Yarkovsky effect describes a small force on a rotating object in space from diurnal, momentum-carrying thermal photons from the Sun. This small force builds up over time, resulting in non-gravitational orbital perturbations for small bodies like meteoroids and asteroids. When Bennu is nearest to the Sun, this tiny force is thought to be the equivalent of the weight of three grapes on Earth (Neal-Jones & Stolte 2014).

sample of the surface material, or regolith, of Bennu². Properties of a regolith sample from an asteroid like Bennu can enlighten theories of early planet formation and the origins of life.

The specific instruments responsible for the collection of scientific data while OSIRIS-REx is in orbit around Bennu include a Camera Suite (OCAMS) for surface imaging, optical navigation, global mapping, and sample acquisition documentation, a laser altimeter (OLA) for topographical information, a visible and infrared point spectrometer (OVIRS), a thermal emission point spectrometer (OTES), and an X-ray imaging spectrometer (REXIS), the instrument which is the focus of this paper.

The Touch-and-Go Sample Acquisition Mechanism (TAGSAM) is responsible for capturing at least 60g³ of regolith via shooting a “puff” of nitrogen gas at loose regolith and collecting material from the cloud of regolith that arises. There will be enough nitrogen gas for three sampling attempts.

The predicted timeline for the OSIRIS-REx mission includes a launch in September of 2016, sampling in 2019, and return to Earth in 2023 (Lauretta, et al. 2012).

²Missions Haybusa returned a small sample of 1500 grains of asteroid 25143 Itokawa in 2010 and Hayabusa2 is meant to sample asteroid (162173) 1999 JU3 and return 60mg in 2020 (Hayabusa 2014). OSIRIS-REx will be the third mission to return a sample, but the first to return a 60g-2kg size sample (Jaesub 2014).

³The sample return capsule can carry up to 2 kg of material of grains as large as 2cm (Lauretta, et al 2012).

1.2. Bennu

The target of the OSIRIS-REx sample return mission is an Apollo near-Earth asteroid, Bennu. Bennu is one of the best studied near-Earth asteroids because of its brightness and nearby (1.3 AU) orbit. With many of its physical parameters determined (Hergenrother, et al. 2014), Bennu made an ideal, low mission cost target. A six year period, nearby orbit, and low eccentricity and inclination can allow for regolith capture; the distance is close enough for a relatively economic space probe voyage and the asteroid's large size gives it a slow enough spin (about a 4.3 hour rotational period) for a probe to sample regolith without being batted away. Thermal IR measurements and radar polarization ratio measurements provide evidence for loose regolith material with an average grain size of 2-4cm (Lauretta, et al 2012). The returned regolith sample will be of particular interest. Bennu is thought to be an asteroid version of a CI or CM chondrite and elemental composition data and mapping from REXIS will help determine which analog meteorite class is a better fit. A carbonaceous chondrite is a more primitive object which is rich with carbon and potentially with organic molecules and amino acids as well. It is hoped that the return sample will reveal Bennu to be an organics-rich asteroid which will inform theories on planet formation as well as the evolution of life on Earth. It is also hoped the composition of Bennu will entice economically geared missions to harvest resources from it and similar asteroids. However, the properties that make Bennu an ideal science and potentially economic target also make the asteroid one of the most hazardous known. Its diameter about 500m, mass of about 6×10^{10} kg, and its orbit can place it as close as 0.0032 AU from the Earth (Hergenrother, et al. 2014). It is thought to have a 10^{-3} probability of impacting the Earth in the 22nd century (Lauretta, et al. 2010). Observing the distribution of thermal re-emission due to incident solar energy, an effect that causes orbit perturbation known as the Yarkovsky effect, will allow a more precise calculation of the probability of impact (Hergenrother, et al. 2014). If the probability of impact proves to be high, detailed data

on the composition and structure of Bennu gained from the OSIRIS-REx mission will allow for the formulation of hazard reduction plans.

1.3. REXIS

A joint endeavour of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) and the Harvard-Smithsonian Center for Astrophysics (CfA), REXIS is an instrument that will acquire a global X-ray map of elemental abundances on Bennu. REXIS began as a proposal submitted by Harvard and MIT to the OSIRIS-REx team for the NASA funded competition for a student project to incorporate into the OSIRIS-REx mission. The project has since involved over 50 students at MIT (where the hardware is being built) and 3 at Harvard (where the performance and imaging simulations have primarily been carried out). The purpose of the instrument is to measure the elemental composition of the regolith on Bennu, focusing on the ratios of elements such as magnesium, iron, sulfur, and silicon, which are the elements of interest when classifying meteorites. These elements fluoresce between 0.5 and 7.5 keV, which is the energy range chosen for REXIS to collect. A requirement for REXIS is to be able to measure these global ratios within 25% for that of a CI chondrite illuminated by the quiet Sun (a 4 MK, A3.3 Sun) within 420 hours of observation time, which is enough to distinguish between meteorite types (Inamdar et al. 2014). Knowing the composition and composition distribution of Bennu will allow for an analog meteorite classification of Bennu and will provide context for the global representation of the returned regolith sample. REXIS will reconstruct the elemental abundance ratios by observing X-ray fluoresced material under the influence of solar X-rays and map these abundances at scales larger than 10 meters, with a goal of 50-200m distribution scales over a period of 40 days.

The X-ray spectrum measured by REXIS will be a function of both the elemental abundances on Bennu and the Solar state during the measurement. To remove the effect

solar variation would have on the spectra, REXIS is actually composed of two subassemblies: The primary imaging spectrometer and the Solar X-ray Monitor (SXM). The imaging spectrometer will observe X-ray fluorescence caused by incident solar X-rays directed at Bennu, and the SXM will monitor the solar X-rays directly, in order to account for emission variability from the Sun and not due to Bennu’s composition.

Other factors that may influence the gathered X-ray spectra include the X-ray detector characteristics, geometric parameters of the observations, and our ability to accurately calibrate the received data. Onboard ^{55}Fe calibration sources with radiation strengths that will ensure a 15 eV spectral gain accuracy within an hour will allow precision measurements of other elemental line features observed from Bennu. This paper will account for the ^{55}Fe calibration source characteristics. It will describe the onboard calibration process of the spectrometer CCD, the geometry of the calibration sources, and the recommended activity level of the sources to obtain a 15 eV spectral gain accuracy per hour.

2. The Primary Imaging Spectrometer

The primary soft X-ray (0.5-7.5 keV) imaging spectrometer is 37cm by 20cm and houses 4 CCD-41s manufactured by MIT Lincoln Laboratory with a circular, coded element aperture mask of randomly arranged pixels (with 1.536mm pixels and 21’ resolution) mounted on top of the tower (See Figure 1). The spectral information is stored in 9 bit energy values over 0.5 to 7.5 keV, creating 15 eV bins. The three key elements of the imaging spectrometer are the CCDs, the calibration sources, and the coded aperture mask.

A CCD is a semiconductor doped such that electrons freed via the photoelectric effect can be held until instrument readout, yielding instrument signal called Data Numbers (DN)

Fig. 1.—: The primary imaging spectrometer of REXIS. The instrument is 12.6in x 5.6in x 7.9in. The coded aperture mask is located under the closed radiation cover at the top of the tower. The radiation cover will protect the CCD-41s from damaging radiation during space flight and will open prior to observing Bennu. Radioactive calibration sources are placed along the edges of the CCD and is shown more precisely in Figure 2. The radiation source mounted on the cover will fully illuminate the CCD to detect any radiation damaged pixels after the trip to Bennu. The 10 sources surrounding the CCD will only partially illuminate the CCD, functioning to monitor the global and spatial gain variation throughout scientific observation.

Fig. 2.—: A closer view of the Detector Assembly Module (DAM) on REXIS. The DAM is 37cm by 20cm. Here, the top and side ^{55}Fe sources (shown in red) are mounted such that the radiation target area is always split between CCDs or the nodes of the CCDs to help detect CCD by CCD or node by node gain variations.

or Analog to Digital Units (ADUs) per pixel location which relates to the energy of the incident X-ray (Howell 2006). A CCD's response to incident flux is linear so that we can relate the charge collected in each pixel to the energy of the photon. The relation of the number of accumulated electrons in a pixel during an exposure and the output signal in ADU determines the gain of a CCD which is used as our conversion factor between the number of electrons and the number of ADUs reported by the CCD. By measuring the gain using X-rays of known energy we can determine the energy of other X-ray photons and deduce what material may have emitted the photons. For REXIS, this is done with radioactive calibration sources, ^{55}Fe , placed around the CCD. ^{55}Fe is known to emit photons at 5.89 keV. This will let us keep track of the detector gain under environmental variation.

However, because these sources decay with a half life of 2.7 years, there must be a high enough activity of the ^{55}Fe source placed by the detector to provide gain measurements within 15 eV accuracy per hour throughout OSIRIS-REx’s journey, about 4.5 years. These sources must emit enough counts to allow the determination of global gain variation within an hour and regional gain variation within 10 hours, both to within a 15 eV accuracy⁴, as required by REXIS. A recommendation of the amount of ^{55}Fe to place adjacent to the CCD is the motivation for this analysis.

The back-illuminated CCD-41s in use on REXIS are a model previously flown on the Suzaku X-ray imaging Spectrometer (XIS). It has 24 micrometer pixels in a 1026x1024 arrangement and a 220 nm layer of aluminium over its top surface which blocks out optical light but not X-rays. After the CCD integrates electrons produced by incident X-rays for a set time of 4 seconds, the charges are quickly transferred into two frame store areas and then read out by one of four output nodes (each CCD-41 is composed of 4 rectangular nodes) by a serial register while the next set of data is being taken. The time from imaging to frame store is about 10ms. The signal is then digitized with a 12 bit analog to digital converter. REXIS has 4 CCD-41s in a 2x2 arrangement. The integration and readout of each CCD occurs in parallel (within 200ms of each other) and the raw CCD frames from all 4 CCDs are transmitted as a single array which is later pared down into an event list that is efficient to transfer back to Earth in a frame processing procedure (Smith, et al. 2014).

An interesting feature of the CCD-41s used is their space-row charge injection (SCI) ability. Radiation from space can be damaging to CCDs and cause an efficiency reduction in moving charges from pixel to pixel during readout (charge transfer inefficiency). This leads to a reduction of gain and spectral resolution. SCI fills up charge traps that are

⁴The gain also depends on temperature. The value of 15 eV was determined to be a stable gain over the course of an an hour (Inamdar et al. 2014).

caused by radiation damage with injected charge, increasing the charge transfer efficiency and stabilizing the gain and spectral resolution (Smith, et al. 2014).

The coded aperture mask is what makes REXIS an imaging spectrometer. It allows for the locations of measured abundance ratios to be determined. When an X-ray photon enters through the coded aperture mask at an angle, the shadow pattern cast by the mask on the detector is recorded. Knowing the precise pattern of the mask and the shadow, we can statistically deduce the angle of the incident X-ray photon. This lets us re-project the photon onto Bennu, giving a location on a 50m scale for the element which emitted the photon. Having a coded aperture does block about 0.6 of the incoming photons (Inamdar et al. 2014).

Other calibration needed to produce an accurate spectra include that of the cosmic X-ray background (CXB) and of instrumental background intrinsic to REXIS. The field of view of the detector extends over the horizon of Bennu, so it will observe some incident cosmic X-rays. Prior to scientific observations, REXIS will collect calibration data of the CXB for 3 hours. The instrumental background will be accounted for with 112 hours of observation prior to opening the radiation cover.

3. Experiment description

To accurately measure the photon count rate of our calibration source and the energy resolution of our CCD we tested an engineering model (an instrument mock up for design testing purposes) within a vacuum chamber at the MIT Space Systems Laboratory with the ^{55}Fe sources in place. Two of these tests are discussed in this paper. The first test occurred on July 25th, 2014 with one CCD in place and the surrounding top and side sources of 50nCi of ^{55}Fe . On October 3rd, we tested a different CCD with only three nodes, two top

sources (203 nCi each), and one side source (101 nCi of ^{55}Fe). There was also an additional source apparent in region 5 in Figure 6 but it is not analyzed in this paper. For both tests, a solution of $^{55}\text{FeCl}$ was deposited in each source location, allowed to evaporate, and sealed with a layer of epoxy. The initial activity amounts were chosen based on a computer simulation including factors like quantum efficiency and some geometrical properties of the source locations (Jaesub 2014). However, the simulation did not account for absorption due to the epoxy used to seal the sources in place or for other geometrical aspects such as self collimation due to the source holders. For this reason, we will later solve for this geometric factor from the data collected.

4. Analysis

4.1. Counts

4.1.1. *The Grading Scheme*

The data gathered by the CCD-41 array on REXIS is pared down into an event list that is smaller and easier to transfer back to Earth for data analysis. The processing of CCD data to event list involves six steps: overclock correction, bad pixel removal, bias map subtraction, generation of a candidate X-ray event list, filtering the list to find X-ray events, and event grading. The resulting event list is composed of an X and Y location of the event on the detector as well as the energy detected and grade in which the event was classified. Here we will be concerned with the last step, event grading, and assume the previous steps were performed correctly.

The classification scheme for assigning a grade value to an event is an attempt to discern how the incident photon's energy was distributed over the CCD's pixels. A grade ranging from 0 to 7 is assigned to an event to describe how the charge from a single X-ray

has been split between two or more pixels. If the photon lands on the middle of a pixel in the CCD it does not generate electron spillage into any nearby pixel and receives a grade of 0. Higher grades describe how many and the location of other pixels where the electrons have spilled (See Figure 3). If the electrons generated by an X-ray event are split over more than one pixel, then those electrons must be added to recover the total number of electrons generated by the photon. Though this includes the unfortunate addition of pixel noise, it is only by finding the total number of electrons that we can deduce the energy of the original X-ray, and thus the material from which the X-ray originated. This summed energy value is called the pulse height of the event. An event threshold (ET) of a certain energy determines if a pixel is flagged as having received an event and a secondary threshold (ST) of a lower energy along with the arrangement of ST flagged pixels determines if the event may have been split over more than one pixel. The ET and ST are independently set for each node on the CCD. In this analysis the ST value is chosen per region to maximize the number of proper events. Events classified as grade 7 have geometries such that it is both unlikely the event came from a single X-ray and unclear how to combine the energies to recover the original event if it did (See Figure 3). Consequently, events classified as grade 7 are unusable and usually unphysical. The ST for which the largest number of events are recoverable is the ST which minimizes the number of grade 7 events. Figures 4 and 5 show the peak ST calculations. In addition to the ET which sets a lower limit on what energies are counted as X-ray events, there exists an upper limit to reject cosmic ray events.

Fig. 3.—: From the raw CCD frame, a program calculates if a pixel has charge greater than any of its neighbors that is above a predetermined event threshold (ET). Here, the red pixel is the triggered pixel and the blue is a neighboring pixel with energy above the split threshold (ST). The gray pixel is a pixel above the ST but unlikely to contain part of a split event due to its location in relation to the other triggered pixels. If a pixel is in the N, E, W, or S position and has an energy that exceeds the ST, then its energy is added to the central pixel to recover the total energy of the event. If the pixel is in the NW, NE, SW, or SE position, it is included only if its and both of its adjacent pixel energies exceeds the ST. This ensures the energies we are adding are more likely from a split photon than two photons received close together.

Fig. 4.—: The number of events in each grade as a function of the ST chosen over all nodes. The ST that minimizes grade 7 events while not transforming every event into a grade 0 (and thus losing all events that were split over more than one pixel) seems to be between 25 and 75 ADUs. Though this graph allows us to see the interaction between ST and the number of recovered events, finding the peak ST on a node by node basis as it reveals instrumental variation (See Figure 5) is more useful.

Fig. 5.—: This plot shows the number of events detected over all grades for six CCD regions per ST. Regions 1 and 6, 2 and 4, and 3 and 5 are located on the same nodes, with the lower numbered region closer to the readout edge and the higher farther away (See Figure 6 for the locations of the regions).

4.1.2. Region and Energy Cuts

Fig. 6.—: A scatter plot of the events over the X-Y locations of the detector. The regions of event density along the edges of the CCD correspond to target areas of the ^{55}Fe calibration sources. The regions are labeled for convenience. Note, only regions 0-3 are used in calculations.

A scatter plot of event triggers maps the physical locations of each event as shown in Figure 6. From this graph, we can see where the target areas for our ^{55}Fe calibration sources are located along the edges of the CCD. The calibration sources were strategically placed to reveal node by node and charge transfer efficiency variations in the CCD. These target

areas are labeled 0-3 (see Figure 6) for convenience. Because these ^{55}Fe sources were the only sources involved in the experiment, we can assume all other events to be background noise. For the data analysis, we only consider the events within these numbered regions and so we “cut” out the events not included in these regions. Similarly, because we know the energy of our ^{55}Fe sources is 5.89 keV, we can assume the peak detector energy corresponds to 5.89keV. We place energy “cuts” around the detector energy peak to ward off noisy events which we are not interested in. These energy cuts were determined by looking at a histogram of event energy per region and selecting an energy count range that encapsulated all features surrounding the peak (See Figure 7 and Table 1).

After narrowing down the event list with region and energy cuts we can find the rate of events which occurred per region. We need to consider the geometry of the instrument in hindering the events detected, the decay of ^{55}Fe , how often the emission of ^{55}Fe is the 5.89 keV energy emission, and the quantum efficiency of the detector. The relation between the number of events or counts and the activity level of the source is given by

$$N = \left(\frac{f_{Geo} \cdot f_{QE} \cdot f_{em}}{2^{T_E/T_0}} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{37Bq}{nCi} \right) \cdot R \cdot T$$

$$= 2.83 \cdot f_{Geo} \cdot R \cdot T$$
(1)

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 N &= \text{the detected count} \\
 f_{Geo} &= \text{the geometric factor originally estimated by simulation} \\
 f_{QE} &= \text{the quantum efficiency of the detector (0.9)} \\
 f_{em} &= \text{5.89 keV X-ray emission fraction per decay (0.27)} \\
 T_E &= \text{Time from assembly to arrival at Bennu (4.5 yrs)} \\
 T_0 &= \text{The half life of } ^{55}\text{Fe (2.7 yrs)} \\
 R &= \text{the activity of the source at the assembly in nCi} \\
 T &= \text{integration time in seconds}
 \end{aligned}$$
(2)

Fig. 7.—: An example energy histogram. This particular graph looks at how many grade 0 events there are per each energy bin (of 50 ADU width) for region 0. The energy cuts for this region would correspond to 1100 to 1650 ADUs.

Originally, our unknowns for determining the activity of the source needed given our variables were N , f_{Geo} , and R . After performing our two tests with some selected R we observed N and so can calculate f_{Geo} . With a precise value for f_{Geo} we can relate the number of counts per second we need to achieve our 15 eV gain variation accuracy per hour. This will allow a recommendation of how much ^{55}Fe should be present to meet the required rate of 0.056 counts per second at the time of assembly and 0.017 counts per second at the time of observation to accurately calibrate spectra (Jaesub 2014). Our results are summarized in Table 2.

Table 1:: A summary of the chosen region and energy cuts and ST for the data analysis. Note regions 0-3 are the same in both tests. The ST which recovers the most events, calculated in Figure 4, is a measure of noise since it minimizes the number of grade 7 events, which are probably “noisy” rather than physical. The higher the peak ST needed to eliminate the “noisy” grade 7 events, the noisier the region. We see the CCD used in the October 3rd test was much noisier than the one in the July 25th test. From looking at the ST in each region and the location of the regions (See Figure 6) we can see there is a much higher ST (and therefore more noise) the farther the region is from the readout location. Other variations in ST may be due to the characteristics of the individual node.

Region Number	Region Cut (pixels)	Energy Cut (ADU)	Peak ST (ADU)
<i>141003.test₁.fits</i>			
0	[250,325,0,75]	[1100, 1650]	44
1	[750,810,0,75]	[1300,1675]	34
2	[810, 875, 0, 75]	[1200,1600]	29
3	[810, 1100, 825, 1200]	[600,1600]	98
<i>140725.test₁.fits</i>			
0	[250,325,0,75]	[1250, 1600]	24
1	[750,810,0,75]	[1200,1700]	67
2	[810, 875, 0, 75]	[1300,1800]	32
3	[810, 1100, 825, 1200]	[1000,1800]	74

Table 2:: Reccommended Activity Levels. We find the recommended values of the top sources and side sources vary greatly, but that within the categories there is not as much variation. The variation within the top source category could be attributed to the manner in which the epoxy was applied or an incorrect assumption of a uniform 90% quantum efficiency. Note the high activity recommendation for region 1 on the July 25th test. This is due to the very few counts in that region. With more observation time, the recommended rate may be similar to region 0 and region 2. Region 3 recommended activity level should be taken with caution as further analysis showed this region to have large variation in gain.

Region	R	T (sec)	N	Calculated f_{Geo}	N/s	Recommended R (nCi)
<i>141003.test₁.fits</i>						
0	203.0	7992.0	296.0	2.029e-05	0.037	296
1	203.0	7992.0	306.0	2.098e-05	0.038	286
2	203.0	7992.0	229.0	1.570e-05	0.029	382
3	101.0	7992.0	1888.0	2.601e-04	0.236	23
<i>140725.fe55₁.fits</i>						
0	50.0	11992.0	157.0	2.912e-05	0.013	206
1	50.0	11992.0	31.0	5.750e-06	0.003	1044
2	50.0	11992.0	158.0	2.931e-05	0.013	205
3	50.0	11992.0	1556.0	2.886e-04	0.130	21

4.2. Spectral

Fig. 8.—: The expected spectrum of ^{55}Fe . In our analysis we see both the Mn K α and Mn K β energies, but we are interested in Mn K α for calibration purposes.

c).

e).

g).

d). Not enough counts

f).

h).

Table 3:: For a mixed model Gaussian fit, we see a) and b) (region 0 for the October 3rd and July 25th tests, respectively) have the best goodness of fits. Plots c) and d) correspond to region 1, and e) and f) region 2. For d), or region 1 in the July 25th test, there were not enough counts to plot and fit our model. This could be due to misalignment of the source, the collimator, and the node boundary of the CCD. Plots g) and h) are ill fit, probably due to in-region gain variation and possibly inefficient charge transfer.

The expected spectrum of ^{55}Fe is shown in Figure 8. We see both Mn $K\alpha$ (5.89 keV) and Mn $K\beta$ (6.49 keV) emissions in our data. Subsequently, we chose to fit our data with a mixed Gaussian model, using the python package PyMix. The results are shown in Table 3.

We assume a Poisson distribution model of our events and take a Gaussian approximation to calculate the error in the peak, our standard deviation. For a Gaussian, the relation between the standard deviation and the Full Width Half Max (FWHM) is $2\sqrt{2\ln(2)}\sigma \approx 2.355\sigma$, and these values are shown in Table 4.

The precision of the mean depends on the number of events observed in a distribution. The uncertainty in measured centroid of the Gaussian peak is a function of N : $\sigma_c = \frac{\sigma}{\sqrt{N}}$ where σ is the standard deviation and N is the number events under the Gaussian (Gedcke 2001). Our requirement is that this error of the centroid of the peak is within the 15 eV at $3\sigma_c$ for a 10 hour integration for a single source. The $3\sigma_c$ values for the Mn $K\alpha$ peak for regions 0-2 are listed in Table 4. Region 3 for both tests and region 1 for the July 25th test were not fit well enough for this calculation to be meaningful.

Our goodness of fit measure for our spectral analysis is Pearson’s chi-squared test from which we report a reduced chi-squared value. Our procedure is as follows: calculate

Table 4: We find the recommended values of the top sources and side sources vary greatly, but that within the categories there is not as much variation. The variation within the top source category could be attributed to the manner in which the epoxy was applied or to the sensitivity of the CCD at the target. Here σ_c is for a 10 hour integration time and μ is the centroid of the Gaussian fit of the Mn $K\alpha$ peak.

Region	μ (ADU)	Gain (eV/ADU)	σ (keV)	$3\sigma_c$ (eV)	FWHM (keV)	χ_r^2
141003.test ₁ .fits (7992.0 second duration)						
0	1346.83	4.38e-03	0.144	12.94	0.34	0.97
1	1389.06	4.25e-03	0.104	9.39	0.24	0.81
2	1347.82	4.38e-03	0.109	11.29	0.26	0.40
3	1160.06	5.09e-03	0.396	13.19	0.93	9.75
140725.fe55 ₁ .fits (11992.0 second duration)						
Region	μ (ADU)	Gain (eV/ADU)	σ (keV)	$3\sigma_c$ (eV)	FWHM (keV)	χ_r^2
0	1484.96	3.97e-03	0.063	9.72	0.15	0.99
2	1485.23	3.97e-03	0.076	11.08	0.18	0.51
3	1461.06	4.04e-03	0.397	22.46	0.93	9.02

the chi-squared statistic, determine the degrees of freedom of the statistic, and divide the statistic by the degrees of freedom to find the reduced chi-squared value.

Our chi-squared statistic is $\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{(O_i - E_i)^2}{(1 + \sqrt{0.75 + O_i})^2}$ where O_i is the observed counts, E_i the expected counts or model prediction, and n the number of bins. We take the Poisson distribution error to be approximated by Neil Gehrels’ method (Gehrels 1986) due to our low number of counts overall. For both tests we take 20 to be n and have 14 degrees of freedom.

5. Conclusion

From this analysis, we find that to ensure that the activity level of the ^{55}Fe sources is adequate for in-flight calibration, each region should have the activities list in Table 2. We see that the activity level of the sources used in the October 3th test were adequate to determine $3\sigma_c$ to at least 15 eV (See Table 4). The level of activity in region 0 for the July 25th test was inadequate, and in region 1, unknown. Region 2 in this test has adequate activity level to determine $3\sigma_c$ to at least 15 eV. The side source covering Region 3 also appears to have sufficient counts but the large gain variation in the spectrum as shown in Table 3 requires sub-division of the data for proper determination of the spectral gain for the region. The flight model CCDs are expected to have more uniform response.

We also find the spectral resolution and gain per source region with our Gaussian mixture model fit (See Table 4).

We notice that region 3, the side source region, has a larger region size, a larger peak ST, and ill-fitted model when compared with the top source regions. The larger region illuminated by the side source is probably due to the geometry of its collimator, indicated by its larger geometric factor (See Table 1). A larger ST implies a “noisier” region. This may be due to inefficient charge transfer, since region 3 is the region farthest away from the readout location on the CCD. Finally, we see that our Gaussian mixture model failed at fitting the spectra from region 3 in both tests. This is probably due combined factors of a small data set, in-region variation, inefficient pixel charge transfer, and choice of bin size.

We also note that the CCD used in the first test (July 25th) seemed to have a more standard gain value across the regions than the one used in the second test (October 3th). The spectral resolution requirement at 5.89 keV is less than 0.25 keV in FWHM. Table 4 shows that some sections of the CCD used in the July test meets the spectral resolution requirement, while none of the regions in the October test meet the requirement.

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